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Potentiometric Studies of Oxidation of Carbohydrate (Glucose, Galactose, Arabinose, Ribose and Xylose)

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THE determination of carbohydrates with periodic acid has been attempted, both by visual and potentiometric methods. It has been found, however that the potentiometric method (being successful only by the direct procedure with the reductant in the cell) was useful only in conjunction with visual procedure.

The carbohydrates have been determined by a number of methods¹⁻⁵ but no work seems to have been done to determine these compounds by periodate using potentiometric methods. Here, the determinations of these compounds, both by visual and potentiometric methods, have been attempted by the authors.

Below is given a summary of the results obtained of oxidation of glucose, galactose, arabinose, ribose and xylose with periodate, both by visual and potentiometric methods (Table 1).

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Compound	Compound taken gm	Compound found by visual titration method (gm)	Compound found by potentiometric method (gm)
1.	Glucose	0.02252	0.02246	0.02218
2.	Galactose	0.02251	0.02245	0.02248
3.	Arabinose	0.01877	0.01875	0.01892
4.	Ribose	0.01978	0.01876	0.01882
5.	Xylose	0.01977	0.01878	0.01892

The results show that in the cases of oxidation of glucose, galactose, arabinose, ribose and xylose, comparable results were obtained by visual and potentiometric titration methods.

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A Rapid Method for the Estimation of Isoniazid with Dichloramine-T and Dichloramine-B

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ISONIAZID (pyridine-4-carboxylic acid hydrazide), a well-known antituberculosis drug, can be assayed through a number of titrimetric and potentiometric methods and most of them are based on the oxidation of the hydrazide group to nitrogen, except the nitrite method¹ which depends on a diazotisation reaction. A recently published method² is based on the indirect potentiometric determination of isoniazid with a chloramine-T ion selective electrode.

In continuation of our work on oxidation studies with organic chloramines²⁻⁴, the present paper reports a detailed investigation of the reaction of isoniazid with dichloramine-T (DCT) and dichloramine-B (DCB) in partially aqueous medium. Isoniazid can be oxidized by DCT and DCB with a four electron change within five minutes, when an excess of oxidant is present in the reaction mixture. Direct titration (visual or potentiometric in presence of KBr in acid medium) of isoniazid with the oxidants was found to be slow and not practicable. Hence, a back titration procedure was employed. The procedure described here is simple, rapid and accurate and can be successfully employed for the determination of isoniazid in pharmaceutical products.

Experimental

Reagents: Recrystallized isoniazid (Koch-light, England) was used. Solution of isoniazid in triply distilled water was standardized⁵. DCT was prepared by the method of Jacob and Nair¹⁰. Chlorination of aqueous solution of chloramine-B⁴ gives good samples of DCB⁶. Approximately decinormal solutions of DCT and DCB were prepared in glacial acetic acid containing 10% v/v acetic anhydride and were standardized by the iodometric method. All other reagents were of accepted grades of purity.

Preliminary studies: Known aliquots of isoniazid solution were added to a known excessive volume of DCT or DCB in an iodine flask at room temperature (30°). The reaction mixture was set aside for various intervals of time with occasional shaking and the maximum standing time being one hour. Then the excess of DCT or DCB was determined by iodometric back titration. It was found that the oxidation of isoniazid was rapid and stoichiometric within five minutes, by an excess of either of the oxidant.

Recommended procedure: Take a sample containing 4-40 mg of isoniazid and dissolve it in 10-15 ml of water. Add the aqueous solution to 25 ml of